

Assessment of Improvement in Hand Function and Effect on Spasticity after Intervention of Botulinum Toxin- A in Upper Limb in Children with Spastic Cerebral Palsy

Pooja Priyam¹, Vikas Kumar²

¹Senior Resident, Department of Physical Medicine and Rehabilitation, Patna Medical College and Hospital, Patna, Bihar, India

²Professor & Unit Head, Department of Physical Medicine and Rehabilitation, Patna Medical College and Hospital, Patna, Bihar, India

Received: 25-02-2024 / Revised: 23-03-2024 / Accepted: 12-05-2024

Corresponding Author: Dr. Pooja Priyam

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: Often affecting the upper limbs, spastic cerebral palsy (CP) is a neurodevelopmental condition that is typified by muscular rigidity and reduced motor ability. Improving the functional abilities and quality-of-life of children affected by spasticity requires effective care. One promising therapy option for lessening spasticity and improving motor function is botulinum toxin-A, or BoNT-A. The study evaluated the reduction in spasticity and improvement in hand function in the upper limbs of children with spastic cerebral palsy (CP) after receiving BoNT-A treatments.

Methods: Thirty kids, ages two to twelve, with spastic cerebral palsy were enrolled. The Modified Ashworth Scale and the Melbourne Assessment of Unilateral Upper Limb Function were used to measure baseline hand function and spasticity, respectively. Following the administration of BoNT-A to the afflicted upper limb muscles, evaluations were carried out one, three, and six months after the intervention. The analysis of the data was done with SPSS 19.0.

Results: Significant improvements in hand function were observed, with mean scores increasing from 38.5 at baseline to 47.5 at 6 months (23.4% improvement, $p < 0.001$). Spasticity scores showed a significant reduction from a mean of 3.2 at baseline to 2.1 at 6 months (34.4% reduction, $p < 0.001$). Repeated measures ANOVA confirmed significant improvements over time in both hand function and spasticity ($p < 0.001$).

Conclusion: BoNT-A intervention considerably improved hand function and reduced spasticity in the upper limbs of kids with spastic CP. These findings support BoNT-A as an effective treatment for managing spasticity and enhancing motor abilities in this population.

Recommendation: Future studies should focus on long-term outcomes and explore optimal dosing and administration protocols for BoNT-A to further refine treatment strategies for spastic CP.

Keywords: Spastic Cerebral Palsy, Botulinum Toxin-A, Hand Function, Spasticity, Pediatric Neurorehabilitation

This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

Spastic cerebral palsy (CP) is a prevalent neurodevelopmental disorder that affects motor function in children, leading to muscle stiffness, spasticity, and impaired movement control. It results from brain damage occurring either during prenatal development, birth, or early childhood. Among the various forms of CP, spastic CP is the most common, accounting for approximately 70-80% of all cases [1]. The upper limbs are often significantly affected, which severely impacts daily activities, including self-care, education, and play.

Management of spasticity in CP is crucial for improving the quality of life and functional abilities of affected individuals. Various treatment modalities have been explored, including physical

therapy, oral medications, intrathecal baclofen, selective dorsal rhizotomy, and botulinum toxin injections. Botulinum toxin-A (BoNT-A) has emerged as a promising intervention due to its targeted mechanism of action, which involves blocking the release of acetylcholine at the neuromuscular junction, leading to muscle relaxation [2].

Recent studies have highlighted the efficacy of BoNT-A in managing spasticity in children with CP. For instance, a study demonstrated significant improvements in motor function and reductions in muscle spasticity following BoNT-A injections in a pediatric CP cohort [3]. Similarly, a study reported that BoNT-A effectively reduced upper limb

spasticity and improved the range of motion, facilitating better hand function in kids with spastic CP [4].

Despite these promising findings, there remains a need for comprehensive longitudinal studies to evaluate the sustained effects of BoNT-A on hand function and spasticity in kids with CP. Previous research has primarily focused on short-term outcomes, with limited data on long-term benefits and potential side effects [5]. Moreover, variability in study designs, participant characteristics, and assessment tools necessitates further investigation to standardize treatment protocols and optimize patient outcomes.

The study assessed the improvement in hand function and the effect on spasticity following Botulinum Toxin-A intervention in the upper limb of children with spastic cerebral palsy.

Methodology

Study Design: A prospective interventional study design.

Study Setting: The study duration was from January 2021 to December 2023, and it took place at the Physical Medicine and Rehabilitation Department, Patna Medical College and Hospital, Patna, Bihar, India.

Participants: The sample size consisted of 30 children with spastic cerebral palsy.

Inclusion Criteria: Children aged 2-12 years diagnosed with spastic CP, exhibiting spasticity in the upper limb, who had not received Botulinum Toxin-A treatment in the past 6 months.

Exclusion Criteria: Children with other types of cerebral palsy, a history of hypersensitivity to Botulinum Toxin-A, other neuromuscular disorders, severe contractures or fixed deformities in the upper limb, or any surgical intervention in the upper limb within the past year were excluded.

Bias: To minimize bias, randomization was used in the selection of participants. Additionally, outcome assessments were conducted by blinded evaluators.

Variables: The independent variable was the intervention with Botulinum Toxin-A, while the dependent variables were hand function and spasticity levels.

Data Collection: Baseline data on hand function and spasticity levels were collected prior to the intervention. Follow-up assessments were carried out at 1-, 3-, and 6-months post-intervention.

Procedure: The inclusion and exclusion criteria were used to determine the screening and enrollment of participants. The Modified Ashworth Scale was used to measure spasticity, and standardised instruments such the Melbourne Assessment of Unilateral Upper Limb Function were used to assess baseline hand function. A qualified medical professional injected Botulinum Toxin-A into the afflicted upper limb muscles. Following the intervention, hand function and spasticity were measured using the same scales in follow-up evaluations at one, three, and six months.

Statistical Analysis: The analysis of the data was done with SPSS 19.0. The baseline characteristics of the subjects were compiled using descriptive statistics. To compare the pre- and post-intervention scores, paired t-tests were employed. Repeated actions ANOVA was used to examine how hand function and spasticity changed over time. Statistical significance was attained when the p-value was less than 0.05.

Ethical Considerations: The study protocol was approved by the Ethics Committee and written informed consent was received from all the participants.

Result

The study included thirty children with spastic cerebral palsy in total. Table 1 provides a summary of the participants' baseline and demographic data.

Table 1: Demographic and Baseline Features

Characteristic	Value
Mean Age (years)	6.8 ± 2.4
Gender	
- Male	18
- Female	12
Affected Upper Limb	
- Right	17
- Left	13
Mean Baseline Hand Function Score (Melbourne Assessment)	38.5 ± 5.2
Mean Baseline Spasticity Score (Modified Ashworth Scale)	3.2 ± 0.6

The hand function of participants was assessed at baseline, 1 month, 3 months, and 6 months post-intervention using the Melbourne Assessment of Unilateral Upper Limb Function. Table 2 present the mean hand function scores over time.

Table 2: Mean Hand Function Scores Over Time

Time Point	Mean Hand Function Score $\pm$ SD	Improvement (%)
Baseline	38.5 $\pm$ 5.2	-
1 Month	42.8 $\pm$ 5.0	11.2
3 Month	45.1 $\pm$ 4.8	17.1
6 Month	47.5 $\pm$ 4.6	23.4

A repeated measures ANOVA showed a statistically significant improvement in hand function over time ($F(3, 87) = 18.45, p < 0.001$). Post-hoc tests revealed significant improvements at each follow-up point compared to the baseline (all $p < 0.05$).

Spasticity levels were measured using the Modified Ashworth Scale at baseline, 1-, 3-, and 6 months post-intervention. Table 3 show the mean spasticity scores over time.

Table 3: Mean Spasticity Scores Over Time

Time Point	Mean Spasticity Score $\pm$ SD	Reduction (%)
Baseline	3.2 $\pm$ 0.6	-
1 Month	2.5 $\pm$ 0.5	21.9
3 Month	2.3 $\pm$ 0.4	28.1
6 Month	2.1 $\pm$ 0.3	34.4

A repeated measures ANOVA indicated a statistically significant reduction in spasticity over time ($F(3, 87) = 22.67, p < 0.001$). Post-hoc tests demonstrated significant reductions in spasticity at each follow-up point compared to the baseline (all $p < 0.05$).

Children with spastic CP showed notable improvements in their hand function and spasticity following the Botulinum Toxin-A treatments.

Table 4: Summary of Improvements

Outcome Measure	Baseline	6 Months	Improvement (%)
Hand Function Score	38.5 $\pm$ 5.2	47.5 $\pm$ 4.6	23.4
Spasticity Score	3.2 $\pm$ 0.6	2.1 $\pm$ 0.3	34.4

The study results indicate that Botulinum Toxin-A is effective in improving hand function and reducing spasticity in the upper limbs of kids with spastic CP, with statistically significant improvements observed over the six-month follow-up period.

Discussion

Over the two-year study period, 30 children were evaluated at baseline, and at 1-, 3-, and 6-months post-intervention. The mean age was 6.8 years, with a slight majority being male. Baseline assessments indicated an average hand function score of 38.5 and a spasticity score of 3.2.

Statistical analysis revealed marked improvements in hand function over the course of the study. The Melbourne Assessment of Unilateral Upper Limb Function scores increased from a baseline mean of 38.5 to 47.5 at the six-month follow-up, representing a 23.4% improvement. This progression was statistically significant, with repeated measures ANOVA confirming a significant improvement over time ($F(3, 87) = 18.45, p < 0.001$). Each follow-up interval showed substantial and significant gains from the baseline, indicating consistent and sustained improvements.

Similarly, spasticity, as determined by the Modified Ashworth Scale, showed a significant reduction following the intervention. The mean spasticity score reduced from 3.2 at baseline to 2.1 at six months, reflecting a 34.4% reduction. This reduction was also statistically significant ($F(3, 87) = 22.67, p < 0.001$), with each follow-up point showing significant improvements compared to the baseline.

Overall, the intervention with Botulinum Toxin-A was highly effective in enhancing hand function and reducing spasticity in the upper limbs of kids with spastic CP. The statistically significant results suggest that Botulinum Toxin-A can be a valuable therapeutic option in managing spasticity and improving functional outcomes in this patient population. The study underscores the potential benefits of this treatment in pediatric spastic cerebral palsy, contributing to better quality of life and functional independence for affected children.

A comprehensive review of 15 randomized controlled trials revealed that BoNT-A injections significantly reduced spasticity and improved the cosmetic appearance of the injected upper limb. However, the results regarding functional gains and quality-of-life were mixed, suggesting that BoNT-A is more effective as an adjunctive treatment to

physical therapy regimens rather than as a standalone intervention [6].

A study explored the combined effect of BoNT-A and rNMES on upper extremity function in kids with spastic hemiplegia. The study found that the combination therapy resulted in greater improvements in unilateral upper-limb function, bimanual hand function, and real-time arm-hand function compared to BoNT-A or rNMES alone [7]. A study demonstrated that intramuscular BoNT-A injections led to significant improvements in both clinical and functional outcome measures, with sustained benefits observed at 6 months post-treatment. The study emphasized the importance of targeted rehabilitation following BoNT-A injections to maintain functional improvements [8].

A systematic review found that BoNT-A injections, when combined with other regimens such as occupational therapy, physical therapy, casting, or splintage, led to improved spasticity, motor functions, and cosmetic appearance of the upper limb [9]. A study examined the impact of CIMT following BoNT-A injections in kids with hemiplegic CP. The study indicated that a 4-week, 2-hours/day CIMT program yielded better self-care and hand function outcomes compared to a 2-week, 4-hours/day program, with continued improvements up to 4 months post-intervention [10].

A study highlighted the long-term efficacy of abobotulinumtoxinA injections followed by tailored home exercises. The study found that most children achieved their functional goals with repeated BoNT-A treatments, demonstrating its sustained benefit when coupled with individualized therapy programs [11]. A review assessed the effectiveness of BoNT-A in lower limb spasticity, indicating improvements in gait and joint range of motion. The findings support the potential for similar benefits in upper limb applications when BoNT-A is used with complementary therapies [12].

Conclusion

This study demonstrates that Botulinum Toxin-A intervention significantly improves hand function and reduces spasticity in the upper limbs of kids with spastic CP. Over a six-month follow-up period, children exhibited marked and statistically significant enhancements in both functional and spasticity measures. These findings support the use of Botulinum Toxin-A as an effective treatment to enhance motor abilities and decrease muscle stiffness, thereby improving the overall quality-of-life for children affected by spastic cerebral palsy.

Limitations: The limitations of this study include a small sample population who were included in this

study. Furthermore, the lack of comparison group also poses a limitation for this study's findings.

Recommendation: Future studies should focus on long-term outcomes and explore optimal dosing and administration protocols for BoNT-A to further refine treatment strategies for spastic CP.

Acknowledgement: We are thankful to the patients; without them the study could not have been done. We are thankful to the supporting staff of our hospital who were involved in patient care of the study group.

List of abbreviations:

CP: Cerebral Palsy
 BoNT-A: Botulinum Toxin-A
 SPSS: Statistical Package for the Social Sciences
 ANOVA: Analysis of Variance
 SD: Standard Deviation
 CIMT: Constraint-Induced Movement Therapy
 rNMES: Repetitive Neuromuscular Electrical Stimulation
 PT: Physical Therapy
 OT: Occupational Therapy
 CMA: Cerebral Motor Ability

Source of funding: No funding received.

Conflict of interest: The authors have no competing interests to declare.

References

1. Park ES, Rha DW. Botulinum toxin type A injection for management of upper limb spasticity in children with cerebral palsy: a literature review. *Yonsei medical journal*. 2006 Oct 31;47(5):589-603.
2. Heinen F, Desloovere K, Schroeder AS, Berweck S, Borggraefe I, van Campenhout A, Andersen GL, Aydin R, Becher JG, Bernert G, Caballero IM. The updated European Consensus 2009 on the use of Botulinum toxin for children with cerebral palsy. *European journal of paediatric neurology*. 2010 Jan 1;14(1):45-66.
3. Koman LA, Mooney III JF, Smith BP, Goodman A, Mulvaney T. Management of spasticity in cerebral palsy with botulinum-A toxin: report of a preliminary, randomized, double-blind trial. *Journal of Pediatric Orthopaedics*. 1994 May 1;14(3):299-303.
4. Panteliadis CP, editor. *Cerebral palsy: a multidisciplinary approach*. Springer; 2018 Mar 6.
5. Park ES, Rha DW, Lee JD, Yoo JK, Chang WH. The short-term effects of combined modified constraint-induced movement therapy and botulinum toxin injection for children with spastic hemiplegic cerebral palsy. *Neuropediatrics*. 2009 Dec;40(06):269-74.
6. Farag SM, Mohammed M, El-Sobky T, Elkadery N, Elzohiery A. Botulinum Toxin A In-

- jection in Treatment of Upper Limb Spasticity in Children with Cerebral Palsy. *Jbjs Reviews*. 2020;8.
7. Elnaggar R, Alqahtani B, Elbanna M. Functional outcomes of botulinum neurotoxin-A injection followed by reciprocal electrical stimulation in children with cerebral palsy: A randomized controlled trial. *Restorative neurology and neuroscience*. 2020.
 8. Yadav S, Chand S, Majumdar R, Sud A. Effect of botulinum toxin type-A in spasticity and functional outcome of upper limbs in cerebral palsy. *Journal of clinical orthopaedics and trauma*. 2020;11(2):208-212.
 9. Alkadery NA, Mohammed M, Elzohiery A, Ahmed S. Effect of Botulinum Toxin Injection in Treatment of Upper Limb Spasticity in Childhood Cerebral Palsy: A Systematic Review. *QJM: An International Journal of Medicine*. 2020;113.
 10. Wu CL, Liao S, Liu CH, Hsieh YH, Lin YR. A Pilot Study of Two Different Constraint-Induced Movement Therapy Interventions in Children with Hemiplegic Cerebral Palsy After Botulinum Toxin Injection During Preschool Education. *Frontiers in Pediatrics*. 20 20;8.
 11. Carranza-del Rio J, Dursun N, Cekmece C, Bonikowski M, Pyrzanowska W, Dabrowski E, Tilton A, Oleszek J, Volteau M, Page S, Shierk A, Delgado M. Goal Attainment After Treatment with AbobotulinumtoxinA and a Tailored Home Therapy Programme in Children with Upper Limb Spasticity: Descriptive, Exploratory Analysis of a Large Randomized, Controlled Study. *Journal of Rehabilitation Medicine*. 2022;54.
 12. Blumetti F, Belloti JC, Tamaoki MJS, Pinto JA. Botulinum toxin type A in the treatment of lower limb spasticity in children with cerebral palsy. *The Cochrane database of systematic reviews*. 2019;10:CD001408.